

Governance of Sarva Shiksha Abhiyan in Arunachal Pradesh: Evidences from the Field

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Abstract: Sarva Shiksha Abhiyan (SSA) is a notable programme introduced by the Central government in 2001 to primarily focus on achieving universal elementary education. The programme was touted as the most comprehensive programme of all times taking into account various aspects of elementary education under its shelter from infrastructure funding to providing quality education, decentralization in management through involvement of local bodies, community mobilization and participation and teacher's training.

Subsequently, the programme has been introduced in Arunachal Pradesh and many changes has been noticed and achieved in the realm of elementary education. Scores of schools have been established, hundreds of teachers appointed and funds released to achieve the aim of universal elementary education in the state. Nevertheless, many problems have been reported as well. Field data analysis revealed that the programme indeed contributed to development and spread of elementary education to a considerable extent. The programme has been a game changer in realizing the aim of universal access to elementary education and enrolment of children but has failed to retain them. Idea of community mobilization and participation has not been realized due to lack of awareness among public. There is inconsistency in implementation of intervention programmes due to delay in disbursing funds and other factors.

Thus, the paper is an effort to examine the implementation status of SSA in the Arunachal Pradesh. It enquires if the programme has been successful in ensuring universal access, universal enrolment and retention of children in schools. How does the community see it and to what extent the community participates in the programme? What are the hindrances if any of such persist is faced by the administrators in executing the programme?

Keywords: Governance, Sarva Shiksha Abhiyan, Arunachal Pradesh, Elementary Education

Introduction

The importance of education in the life of every child has been well recognized in the Declaration of The Rights of Children (1959) which considered education as right of every child. India has been making strides in education sector by making various provisions overtime. The incorporation of Article 45 in Part IV of

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Directive Principles of States Policy (DPSP) in the Indian constitution that provides that there shall be a provision for free and compulsory education for children is known to all. Besides many initiatives have been taken in the subsequent years such as appointment of various educational commissions such as University Education Commission (1952-53), Kothari Commission (1966) etc. and declaration of education policies such as National Education Policy (1968, 1978, 1986 and 1992). Further, various programmes like National Literacy Mission (1986), Operation Blackboard (1987), Mahila Samakhya Programme (1988), District Primary Education (1993) etc. were initiated.

Meanwhile, a major international development took place with the World Declaration on Education for All (EFA) in 1990 at Jomethian, Thailand. India became a signatory to this commitment and it set its target of universal elementary education by 1995. At the national level, the case of *Unnikrishnan vs State of Andhra Pradesh* (1993) further intensified the children's claim on basic education. The Supreme Court of India in its judgment held that all children up to fourteen years of age have the fundamental right to education. It was around this time that the Government of India introduced the 83rd Constitutional Amendment Act (1997) to make education a fundamental right of all children from six to fourteen years of age. Consequently, a programme called Sarva Shiksha Abhiyan (SSA) was introduced to realize the goal of universal elementary education by 2010 in a mission mode manner following a convergent approach.

Subsequently, the Government of India introduced the 86th Constitution Amendment Act, 2002 and inserted Article 21A "Right to Education" in the Indian Constitution. The Article states that the state shall provide free and compulsory education to all children of six to fourteen years in a manner as the state may by law determine. This was further consolidated with the introduction of a bill called the Right of Children for Free and Compulsory Education Bill passed by both the Houses of Indian Parliament and received the President of India's assent on 26th August 2009. It was added in the Statute Book as 'The Rights of Children to Free and Compulsory Education Act (2009). Hence, a new thrust towards attainment of the goal of universal elementary education began in India.

A Brief Background of Sarva Shiksha Abhiyan

Following independence in 1947, the Government of India in its resolve to achieve universal elementary education initiated many steps. For instance, the Kothari Commission (1964) had viewed that primary education is something which requires highest consideration. It suggested for steps like provision of school within an easy distance from every child's home and each state as well as district to have a perspective plan of its own to develop primary education. This resulted in declaration of National Policy on Education (1968) suggesting for a provision of incentives such as mid-day meals, free textbooks and school uniforms to

children from economically distressed families. It also called for a special emphasis on education of Scheduled Caste/Scheduled Tribe/handicapped and women along with involvement of the community to ensure effective implementation. This was further stressed in National Policy on Education (1986) which called for quality education, community involvement and supply of essential equipments under Operation Blackboard. To achieve the target, the National Policy on Education (1992) called for a nationwide mission to ensure universal elementary education by the year 2000.

In the following years, a conference of State Education Ministers was convened in 1998 which recommended for a mission mode approach to pursue the goal of universal elementary education (Kainth, 2006, 3288). Consequently, a national committee under then Union Minister of Human Resource Development along with other education ministers was appointed in 1999. The committee agreed with the idea of mission mode and convergent approach. Thereafter, the cabinet approved the scheme of Sarva Shiksha Abhiyan (SSA) on 16th November, 2000 (Agarwal, 2007, 175). The programme was formally launched in 2001 and revised the target of universal elementary education to 2010.

After its introduction, the programme subsumed all the then existing programmes at the elementary level such as Operation Blackboard, Teacher Education, Non- Formal Education, Mid-Day Meal scheme and so on which dealt with different facets of education. After its introduction, a new element was its holistic vision to develop definite projects for every district. The programme also intended to ensure community mobilization and participation and instill a sense of community ownership among the public by involving local bodies. Thus, SSA is a comprehensive programme in the arena of elementary education. As of now, the programme has been subsumed under the Samagra Shiksha Abhiyan which conjoins school education under one shelter.

Hence, SSA programme was pursued keeping certain goals in perspective such as:

- To bring back all children to schools, alternative schools, education guarantee scheme centers and back to school camps by 2003.
- To allow children to complete five years of schooling by 2007 and eight years of schooling by 2010.
- It also stresses on standard quality of education.
- It yearns to bridge gender and social disparity in primary levels by 2010.
- It endeavours to realize target of universal retention by 2010.

In order to achieve the intended goals, the programme identified certain deliveries. To illustrate a few, it stressed on consolidating existing infrastructure, provide required strength of teachers in every school, ensure universal education facility in all habitations which had not been covered, focus on education of children from weaker sections and bridge digital divide through provision of computers and advanced teaching learning equipment. It also recognized the need of an efficient staff through extensive training. At the same time, to deliver the output, the programme also employed some relevant strategies. These strategies included an institutional reform at the national and state level to devise relevant means to revamp the delivery system.

A sustainable financing system was envisaged through a financial partnership between the central and state governments. Participation of community members became an important measure to ensure effective monitoring. To ensure meaningful planning, habitation planning became the ground for preparation of district plan. Priority was given to education of children such as girls, scheduled caste/ scheduled tribe, children with special needs and other weaker sections of the society. It acknowledges the role of teachers for quality education and ensured their development through resource support from Block Resource Centres, Cluster Resource Centres, exposure tour, institutional training through District Institute of Education and Training (DIETS).

Further some norms of intervention were framed. For example, maintenance of a good pupil-teacher ratio for schools at the primary and upper primary level, creation of school or alternative school facility within 1 km of every habitation and provision for free textbooks under the state plan to all ST/SC/ Girl child with a ceiling of 150 per child. It also talks about provision of funds for school maintenance and repairing under school grant and maintenance grant. It provides for a provision for training of community members limited to eight at max in every village for two days annually along with establishment of Block Resource Centres/ Cluster Resource Centres to provide academic resource support to teachers. It recognizes the need of training of teachers and as such training of teachers into refresher course, in service training and orientation programme were introduced.

As far as financial share is concerned, as of 2015 the ratio of financial share has been decided at 60:40 between the central and other state governments and in case of North Eastern states it is 90:10 (Gohain, The Times of India 2017). Further, the cost of intervention programmes under SSA such as mid- day meals were to be shared. The cost of food grains and transportation is to be borne by the Centre and cost for cooked meal by the state governments. However, the cost for incentives such scholarships and free uniforms would continue but under the state plan for education. (Jha et al 2008, 273). Thus, the programme strives

to establish a congenial environment for children and achieve the goals of universal access, universal enrolment and universal retention in a planned out and effective manner.

Sarva Shiksha Abhiyan in Arunachal Pradesh

SSA in Arunachal Pradesh was introduced during 2001-02. During the first phase the programme was confined to three districts namely, Tirap, Tawang and East Kameng. It was later in 2002 that the rest of the districts were covered (Saroh 2015, 19). Consequently, as a measure of action towards realizing the target of universal elementary education the Government of Arunachal Pradesh passed the Arunachal Pradesh Right of Children to Free and Compulsory Education Rules, 2010. It guaranteed every child in the state a provision for free and compulsory education from 6-14 years of age. Further led to the establishment of hundreds of schools, recruitment of hundreds of teachers, establishment of SSA mission office in every district and introduction of several intervention programmes are undertaken.

Many initiatives were launched such as establishment of Kasturba Gandhi Balika Vidyalaya (KGBVs) for girls from scheduled castes and schedule tribe, monetary incentive like Pratibha Khoj was introduced to ensure their enrolment and retention in schools along with quality education. The government also provided aids such as hearing aids, crutches for disabled, spectacles for children with poor eyesight, braille kit for visually impaired kids, wheel chairs for physically challenged kids and so on. A programme called Digital Computer Aided Learning System was also introduced to enable computer education for innovative learning of subjects such as science, mathematics, english and others. Other incentives in the form of free school uniforms, free textbooks and mid-day meals have also been provided for children in the elementary level (Report of the CAG 2011, 25-32).

However, time and again many problems have been reported in the state. The problems include state of poor infrastructure such as broken desks, benches, ceilings to poor facility of drinking water facilities and toilets; reports of teachers protesting against delay in salary for many months; shortage of subject teachers; irregularity in appointment and inspection and so on. An audit report of 31st March, 2011 further highlighted some grey areas in the elementary education sector. Some of the problems identified were:

- Failure of state government to release its financial share resulting in backlogs of funds which affected intervention programmes under SSA.
- Unauthorized expenditure of 692.70 lakhs against expenditure approved under Project Approval Board.
- Failure of the state to attain target of universal enrolment of children in the schools.

- Illogical deployment of teachers resulting in problem of single teacher schools. For instance, by 2011 about 758 schools was manned by single teachers.
- Presence of at least 76.32% of untrained teachers.
- Above 50% and above lack drinking water facility and about 47% of schools were in wreckful condition.
- Cases of embezzlement reported around whooping 26.95 crores by executing agencies. Such amount was neither refunded nor the work every accomplished.
- Irregularities in supply of mid-day meals, Pratibha khoj, school uniforms and textbooks.

All these implementation issues question the governance of the programme in the state at the ground level.

Universe of the Study

The field work was carried out in Doimukh Circle in Papumpare and Kamba Circle in West Siang. Among the two study areas, Kamba in West Siang district is home to various tribes like Galo, Minyong, Bori, Bokar, Palibo, Ramos and Memba. According to 2011 census, the literacy rate of the district was 66.46%. In contrast Doimukh in Papumpare district is home to the Nyishi tribe with a total literacy rate of the district standing at 79.95%. With regard to development, Kamba circle is comparatively less urbanised as compared to Doimukh whereas the latter is near the capital city and more urban.

With regard to Papumpare district, SSA was introduced in 2001-01. During that year forty primary schools and six upper primary schools were sanctioned which however was not opened. It was only in 2002-03 that twelve primary schools and ten upper primary schools were opened in the district. As of 2017-18, 269 primary schools have been opened, forty-three primary schools have been upgraded to upper primary schools and seventy-five upper primary schools opened and three upgraded to secondary level. Further, till 2017-18, the district has a total of twelve residential schools and teachers' recruitment (cumulative) as on March, 2019 for primary classes is 511. For upper primary classes teachers sanctioned and recruited (cumulative) stands at 112. (Management of Information on School Education (MISE), Papumpare district 2019).

In the West Siang district, SSA was introduced on 13th August, 2001-02 but no schools were sanctioned nor opened. It was during 2002-03 that 10 primary schools were sanctioned and opened under SSA. As of 2018-19, the district has a total of 158 schools out of which 101 of them are primary schools and thirty-eight of them are upper primary schools. The total strength of primary teachers working under SSA is 177

in the district. Further, enrolment of students in class 1-V is 3963 and enrolment in class VI-VIII is 2641. (Unified District Information on School Education (UDISE), West Siang district 2019).

Methodology

With regard to sampling method, purposive sampling method was employed. Purposive sampling method was employed because among the respondents from the community members, parents of the students who were taken as sample respondents were included. Further, SSA implementing authorities, prominent educated people from both the districts were interviewed to understand the various implementation issues and to get a holistic picture of SSA implementation. In addition, sampling method was employed to choose schools feasible to the researcher in the study area for logistical reasons.

As far as sample size is concerned a total of 174 respondents, 87 from each study areas were taken for the study. The samples comprised of five categories of respondents which include 7 SSA Functionaries, 10 Teachers, 10 School Management Committee (SMC) members, 50 community members and 10 students. The primary data was collected through survey of the opted areas employing techniques like interview schedule, telephonic interview, observation and discussions with the respondents. The secondary data was collected from books, articles, official records, journals, newspapers, reports and other available materials.

Field Findings

For field survey, the questions asked ranged from basic awareness regarding the programme and its provisions to knowing their perception as well as suggestions from the respondents. The following section enumerates the findings and results of the field survey.

- During field survey it has been found that the level of awareness among the respondents regarding Sarva Shiksha Abhiyan (SSA) is very low. Those unaware from the community members were mostly the illiterate and lesser educated ones from the community. What is more surprising is that even the School Management Committee members (SMC) and some teachers at the elementary level were not fully aware about the programme and its provisions. When compared between the two study areas though low, awareness about the programme is comparatively better among people in Doimukh than those of Kamba. The possible reason could be that Doimukh being close to the capital city many educated people live here, hence better aware about the program.
- Accessibility to elementary school education among children has improved to a great extent. In both the study areas, every habitation has their own primary and upper primary schools. However, during

field survey it was seen that some schools even though found in the record of running schools were actually defunct. This indicates that action towards achieving the goal of universal access to education by establishing schools in every habitation has improved but is away from being universal.

- As far as enrolment of children is concerned field data show a positive view. In both the study areas be it boy or girl, there has not been any case of children deprived of basic education. According to teachers, SMC, community members and SSA functionaries' enrolment has been going strong and is satisfactory. Those of the parents who could afford had enrolled their children in private schools and rest in government schools. They were of the view that every person today understands the value of education and perhaps that is the reason that enrolment has been satisfactory in both the study areas.
- With respect to retention though comparatively better in Doimukh than in Kamba, some inconsistency has been noticed in both the areas. It has been found that many dropped out from schools due to irregularity of teachers and dissatisfaction with the quality of education provided to them. This can be well ascertained from the instances of defunct schools in the study areas. It has also been seen that after dropping out those who could afford send their children to private school to pursue education. However, those families which could not afford such opportunity were the affected ones. This data indicates that wastage continue till today.
- The status of gender literacy has been found good in both the study areas. Data collected from the field survey as well as discussion indicates that every girl child is enrolled for education by their parents. The girl students and women from the community informed that attitude of family towards education has been positive. They informed that every child is treated equal by their parents in the matters of education. Hence, this show that society's take on education of both the male/female child has been encouraging.
- With respect to intervention programmes under SSA, field data, study of report and discussion held with the respondents reveal that there has been tremendous inconsistency in implementation of these programmes. The implementation of interventions though found better in Doimukh than in Kamba has been irregular. For instance, mid-day meal was not provided regularly to children. The reason being irregular supply of food grains to respective schools. It was also found that though food grains reach but adequate conversion cost was not provided. Sometimes rice was provided but dal was not. In such case, preparation of complete meal is not possible. On the question of textbooks it has been found that many a time's supply of textbooks was delayed. In some cases some subject books never

reached for a session and many times damaged books were received with pages missing. This affects the completion of curriculum in the schools.

- As far as free uniforms are concerned, it was found that many of the uniforms that reached schools were ill fitted. In subsequent years it has been substituted and children were provided some monetary incentive amounting to 350 rupees in lieu of free uniform. However, the problem is that the cost of stitching dress is more than what is provided to them. In such case monetary incentive makes no sense because students are left with no choice but to ask from their parents. Hence, this indicates that approach of government towards intervention programmes has been impractical and fails at the ground level.
- Respondents were asked a question related to satisfaction of infrastructure of government schools in their locality. Majority of the respondents from both the study areas seem to be dissatisfied with the existing infrastructure. This was further evident from the field visit by the researcher. It was found that many schools had broken windows, broken ceilings, distorted blackboards and shaky desks and benches. When asked the reason for such poor condition the teachers, SMC members and SSA officials informed that the maintenance grant provided by the government is not adequate. They also informed that the grant is often delayed that hamper speedy action and results in deplorable condition of schools and its infrastructure.
- When enquired about inspection of schools by the authorities, the community members, some teachers and School Management Committee members informed that inspection is done twice or thrice a year. However, the problem is that the teachers already know of their visits beforehand and they come on the day of inspection while rest of the days they are irregular. Many were of the view that regular visits every month by the authorities is necessary to curb this menace. There have also been some instances of surprise visits from block education officers and block resource coordinators; however, the root of the problem lies in the absence of action from the higher authorities towards irregular teachers. Hence this indicates that administrative vigilance over school management is loose in both the areas.
- During field survey it was seen that digital learning is far from real. It has been found to be a mere announcement of the government and nothing more than that. Out of the ten schools, five each from the respective areas, only one school in Kamba circle was some years back provided with computers. However, it was informed by the School Management Committee during field survey that the school lack regular electricity supplies and no teacher were ever appointed to handle the work. Students also informed that they never received any computer lesson. Hence, this indicates that goal of bridging digital divide is only a paper work.

- With respect to prescribed pupil- teacher ratio of 1:30 for lower primary and 1:40 for upper primary levels, it has been found satisfactory in both the study areas. However, during field survey it was seen that the problem is actually related to lack of subject teachers and not ratio as a whole. Consultation with respondents revealed that dearth of subject teachers was probably one of the reasons for incompleteness of syllabus. Probably this is one of the reasons that students from government school are weak in subjects like science, English and mathematics.
- SSA recognizes community ownership, mobilization and participation as one of the pivotal means for effective delivery of the programme. Data collected from the field survey indicate lack of participation from the community in both the areas. Majority of the general public were not aware of the programme and its provisions. They were never consulted about their role nor were mobilized for participation. Even the SMC members were not fully aware about their role. Further the community members were fully dependent upon the SMC, teachers and SSA officials for management and monitoring of school. This indicates that community participation has failed to percolate in the system.
- From field survey it has also been found that there is lack of training among the teachers in both the areas. This is evident from the data collected as majority of the teachers from both the areas; both regular as well as contractual teachers appointed under Sarva Shiksha Abhiyan (SSA) had very little knowledge about the SSA programme and its provisions. The head teachers of the school are no exception to this. This comes as a surprise because teachers are one of the major stakeholders in achieving the target of universal elementary education and they not being aware of the programme is saddening. Thus, this call for meaningful and intensive training of teachers or else the education system will crumble from within.
- Survey data and observation in the study areas also revealed that many schools lacked proper sanitation and drinking water facilities. Toilets were constructed with no water supply and the schools had no separate toilets for girls and boys. One student informed that because of lack of water supply in the toilets they skip classes. Further due to improper drinking water facility students informed that they bring water bottles from home and in other days resort to tap water for drinking. This indicates the problem of unhygienic conditions in the schools.
- Field survey also revealed that the problem of teacher's irregularity is persisting in both the areas. Overall, the problem is severe in Kamba than in Doimukh. Especially, this trend has been found more in schools away from administrative establishments. An administrator informed that during inspection in a school it was found that some teachers appoint proxy to teach and in return pay some amount as remuneration equivalent to half of their salary. It was also informed by the teachers that

delay in disbursing remuneration and absence of teacher's quarter in posted areas is one of the prime reasons for teachers' irregularity.

- With respect to satisfaction regarding quality of education, respondents from both the areas seem to be dissatisfied with the quality of education provided in the government schools. Many informed that many students of class V and VI from government schools were not able to comprehend better in English and lacked basic knowledge of subjects like Science and Mathematics. In contrast a class II student from a private school was better than those in government schools. This indicates that all in all they lack basic grasp on subjects and goal of providing education of standard quality has not been successful.
- During field visit while discussing with the officials it has been found that there were many defunct schools in both the areas which were in the list of functioning schools. Officials informed that one such reason is low enrolment of children as their parents prefer sending to private schools due to poor infrastructure. Thus, it has been found that long period of un enrolment results in cases of defunct schools affecting not only students and community but also costing the state exchequer.

Discussion

The above findings from the field reveal that the SSA programme in Arunachal Pradesh has brought in tremendous changes in the development and spread of elementary education in the state. It has provided an opportunity to make education a reality for many and reach as many children as possible especially from the economically distressed families. In this respect, progress has been witnessed with respect to accessibility and enrolment of children in the elementary level but these achievements are threatened by the continual menace of wastage which has been known during the study. Over all the implementation of SSA programme has been shallow in both the areas. The Government's aim of instilling a sense of community ownership among public for effective delivery of the programme through active involvement has not been realized. This is probably due to the failure in mobilizing the community for their participation. Non participation of community in implementation is a resultant outcome of lack of awareness which seems to be an administrative inefficiency in handling the same. Special care to physically challenged children through provision of aids to them is highly unsatisfactory because such facilities are not provided every year defeating the purpose of inclusive education.

Decentralization to involve local bodies has also failed in the sense that though local body members are involved as a member of School Management Committee yet they possess little knowledge about their role and are inactive which point towards a culture of careless attitude of administration towards the local bodies.

The goal of providing education of standard quality also seems to be unsatisfactory considering the performance of the students and rate of drop outs resulting in defunct schools. Inconsistency in implementation of intervention programmes such as mid-day meal, free textbooks and uniforms and so on constituting the core elements under SSA has been rampant and is disheartening. Irregularities met in this regard are one of the formidable factors for mediocre result delivered in the state. At a larger context, the programme has not been able to deliver highly as it should have at the grassroots due to political and administrative failure and uninterested attitude of community in handling the programme.

Implication Measures for Policy Making and Governance

The field survey and the data collected thereof and the observations and discussions with the respondents in the study areas makes one realize that SSA requires a revisit to ensure that its goals are achieved. Therefore, some plausible policy implication measures are presented which if initiated may be helpful to overcome existing gaps and aid in improving the machinery for productive and meaningful execution of the programme:

- Awareness among people is vital for any programme to be successful in its implementation. During field survey lack of awareness was found in majority of respondents from all the categories of respondents which has affected the implementation at the ground level. Perhaps this is the reason that they were voiceless with the notion that general public has no right to voice as well as participate in the system. Thus, spreading awareness regarding the programme is vital for optimum delivery of programme at the ground level.
- During field survey it has been seen that the target of creating sense of community ownership for effective implementation of SSA programme has not been effective. To ensure pro-active participation and community mobilization for management of schools, the SMC members should be trained well and generate awareness about their responsibility. It is through them that community could be better dealt with and encouraged for involvement. Hence, this way decentralization in educational management will be more effective.
- Irregularities related to funds such as unauthorized expenditure must be dealt with strongly in order to deter the offenders. Regular auditing and accounting is a needful intervention in this regard.
- It was also found that officials most likely depend on records submitted to them regarding the progress in every district. Considering the administrative irregularities such reports could be way from truth. In this direction regular investigation and evaluation through field visits by the higher authorities will go a long way.

- It has also come to light that gaps regarding implementation of the intervention programmes such as mid-day meal, supply of free textbooks and uniforms on time is due to delay in releasing of funds from the government. From records it has also been known that backlog of funds by the state government has been witnessed on many occasions. Therefore releasing of funds at regular intervals for various purposes under SSA shall be a welcoming step for effective implementation.
- During survey of the study areas and discussion with the SSA officials it has been found that many new schools are opened by the government without proper infrastructure. Eventually such schools are the ones which become defunct. Instead, the government should consolidate the existing schools for quality education rather than opening new ones.
- During interaction with the teachers, it has been found that many of the teachers both regular and contractual were not provided any training. Majority of them did not have any clear idea about the SSA programme. Officials also informed that training depends on release of grants by the government which many times the government fail to do so. Therefore, effective ways must be devised to achieve the target with limited resources. Stances of untrained teachers are a result of lack of resources.
- One common grievance that was reported during field survey is the delay in disbursement of salary to SSA teachers from the state government. The regularized teachers and the contractual teachers perform the same task under one shelter but while the regularized ones get their salary on time the contractual does not. The common excuse is that the government does not have funds. The government must understand that without incentive none will be sincere and dedicated in their work. While it may not be feasible on the part of government to regularize all the contractual SSA teachers at least the government should try to provide their remuneration on time to boost their morale.
- During field survey it was found that the officials rely on school records to assess the performance of the students. Reports can be deceptive at times. Therefore holding tests for students by the officials to examine their performance in language and other basic subjects could go a long way in terms of measuring and ensuring good quality education at the elementary level.

The observations and conclusion provided above is a result of the study and findings based on the two study areas opted. Every area has their unique socio economic and political gaps and as such further similar studies are required at a broader level to translate the broader trends of observation in policy terms to achieve the target of universal elementary education.

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